

DARK TOURISM

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Abstract

The article explores the concept of dark tourism which refers to travel to places related to death, suffering, and tragedy. The dark tourism is more popular in modern society and its origins can be traced back to ancient times. Such as Roman gladiator games and public executions. The article will show different types of dark tourism, including Holocaust tourism, battlefield tourism, prison tourism, cemetery visits and the motivations behind people's interest in such destinations, including curiosity, emotional reflection, and contemplation of mortality. Moreover, the study highlights how modern society often separates people from reality of death, making dark tourism the way to reconnect with and understand human mortality.

Keywords: death-related attractions; Roman gladiatorial games; The Roman Colosseum; correction houses; schadenfreude; thanatopsis

Introduction

The tourism has developed into many different forms in the modern world and one of the most unusual sorts is dark tourism. Dark tourism includes visiting places connected to death, tragedy, suffering and disaster. Even though, this phenomenon has recently gained attention from researchers and the media practice itself is not new. Throughout history people have been attracted to sites of violence and death for religious, educational, or entertainment purposes. In these days, dark tourism involves visits to battlefields, prisons, cemeteries, Holocaust memorials, and disaster sites. This article examines the historical background of dark tourism, its modern development, and the psychological and social motivations that encourage people to visit such places. It also discusses the relationship between dark tourism and contemporary society.

There are an increasingly number of death-related visitor sites, attractions and exhibitions, often trading under the guise of remembrance, education and entertainment, which attract people eager to consume real and commodified death. Indeed, the act of touristic travel to sites of death, disaster and the macabre is becoming a pervasive cultural activity within contemporary society. From enjoying family picnics on battle sites of northern France or purchasing souvenirs of genocide at Ground Zero, to allowing schoolchildren to experience past lives of unfortunate inmates at the Bodmin Jail Centre, are all illustrations of the

seemingly macabre. Consequently, the term 'dark tourism' also known by the rather awkward label of "thanatourism" has entered academic discourse and media parlance. Essentially dark tourism refers to visits, intentional or otherwise, to purposeful and non-purposeful sites which offer the presentation of death or suffering as reason d'être. Likewise, Tarlow identifies dark tourism as visitations to places where tragedies or historically noteworthy death has occurred and that continue to impact our lives.

With increasing attention from the academic community and media alike, this article suggests dark tourism, with its roots in a pre-modern age, is an old concept but with new relevance and consequence for the society in which we reside today. Of course, travel to and experience of events associated with death, pain or suffering is not a new phenomenon. Whilst religious pilgrimages, for emotional and spiritual reasons, have attracted people to sites of death and violence for centuries, tourists have long been drawn, intentionally or otherwise, to death-related attractions. Early examples may be found in the patronage of Roman gladiatorial games. With death and suffering at the core of the gladiatorial product, and its eager consumption by raucous spectators, the Roman Colosseum may be considered one of the first dark tourist attractions.

Other precursors to dark tourism, and before the democratization of travel, may be seen in the public executions of the medieval period up until the 19th century. As public spectacles, executions served as visible reminders of deterrence and retribution. Yet, with the advent of more formalised arrangements to accommodate visiting voyeurs, public executions increasingly took on the characteristics of a spectator event. Indeed, execution sites such as Tyburn boasted specially erected grandstands to offer better vantage points to see the condemned die. Other early examples of dark tourism may be found in the guided morgue tours of the Victorian period, the Chamber of Horrors exhibition of Madame Tussaud, or in 'correction houses' where galleries were built to accommodate fee-paying visitors who witnessed flogging as a recreational activity.

Presently however, dark tourism is manifested in various forms and subsets. These include Holocaust tourism, battlefield tourism, cemetery and internment sites, slavery-heritage, celebrity death sites, and prison tourism. However, it is only recently that dark tourism, in all its manifestations and various shades has become widespread and seemingly more popular. Whilst it remains unclear as to whether the proliferation of dark tourism is due to an increased supply of attractions and sites, or whether consumers are demanding more and more of the

macabre, media inspired or otherwise, death in touristic form is an increasing feature of the contemporary landscape.

It is this demand for the dark tourism product, and the motivation that lies behind it that is of fundamental importance. Whilst there is clearly a need for a much fuller exploration of motivations for dark tourism, in both general and micro-populations, some speculation has already been made. For instance, Seaton and Lennon (2004) suggest that journeys into the realms of death and suffering have two distinct origins. Firstly, they advocate that the existence of *schadenfreude*, a secret pleasure in witnessing the misfortunes of others, may be a prime motivator in people travelling to sites of disaster. Secondly, they suggest *thanatopsis*, the contemplation of one's own death, which also may be a factor at play when people visit dark sites. However, personal contemplation of death in a contemporary world is often negated through a lack of mechanisms that allow confrontation of death. With increased secularisation and change in family structures, medicalization of the death process and privatization of the death industry, death has become institutionally sequestered from contemporary society. Consequently, this apparent absence of death within contemporary society proves a paradox because as mortal finite beings, as we live so we shall die, therefore death is very much present. Thus, dark tourism and its consumption may be a contemporary mechanism for confronting death, hence making absence death present in the sense it allows consumers to undertake *thanatopsis* in a visible and accepted manner. However, to date the dimensions of dark tourism and its consumption have not been fully extracted or interrogated, only assumed. The task now is to reveal the extent of dark tourism, the motivations that lie behind it, and perhaps more importantly its relationship with the wider society in which we reside today.

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